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Abstract: Education is one of the main concepts in pedagogy. During the historical development of society and pedagogy, different approaches to the explanation of this category appeared. First of all, education in the broad and narrow sense is distinguished below.

Key words: education, education process, purpose of education, content of education, general tasks of education, types of education, principles of education, laws of education, process, mental, moral, mindset formation, outlook, physical education, team, children's collective, team education .

Education is the process of comprehensively raising the young generation based on a specific, specific goal and social experience, forming their mind, behavior, worldview.

In a broad sense, education is considered as a social phenomenon, the influence of society on an individual. In this case, education is combined with socialization.

means specially organized activities of pedagogues and students to realize the goal of education in the conditions of the pedagogical process . In this case, the educational activity of pedagogues is called educational work.

The theory of education is an important component of the science of pedagogy and studies the content, principles, laws of the educational process, issues of its organization, methodology, forms, methods, tools, methods and problems.

The educational process is the progress and development of cooperative activities between the teacher and the student (educator and student) organized on the basis of a specific goal.

is an organizational and technical organization of pedagogical activities aimed at forming moral and moral qualities in students, based on a specific goal and social idea.

The specific features of the educational process are as follows:

- clear goal orientation;
- long duration (results of education are not immediately visible);
- continuity (continuous, systematic joint actions of students and the teacher);
- holistic , systematic organization;
- existence of two- way communication and contradictions.

In the process of education, changes such as the development of consciousness, the development of feelings, and the formation of behavioral habits that serve to organize social relations necessary for social life are observed in the personality of the student.

The success of the educational process depends on its goals, forms, methods, tools, existing pedagogical conditions, and the need for self-education and re-education of the individual.

The goal of education is determined on the basis of social order. It explains the essence of the process of organizing a large-scale social movement, from the simplest movement.

The purpose of education is general and individual.

The education process is based on the following laws:

- dependence of education on objective and subjective factors;
- unity and interrelationship of education with personal development;

- activity and attitude are the basis and main source of formation of socially significant qualities of a person;

- the existence of a connection between the mutual educational influence, mutual relations and active activities of the students .

The content of education consists of the essence of social requirements for the formation of a person, and the social and economic development, the nature and level of personal relationships, and the ideas of the society's ideology are determined as a basis.

The influence of upbringing on personality development is seen in the following:

1) under the influence of upbringing , knowledge and information that could not be given by the environment are acquired, skills and competencies related to work and technical activity are formed;

2) due to education , congenital defects are changed and the person matures;

3) it is possible to eliminate the negative effects of the environment with the help of education ;

4) education sets a goal for the future.

Education is a pedagogical process organized for purposeful improvement of the personality, which allows regular and systematic influence on the personality of the student.

includes two interrelated activities - teacher's and student's activities. In the process of education, the student's mind is formed, feelings and emotions develop, and behavioral habits necessary for social life and serving social relations are formed.

Pedagogically correct organization of children's life and activities during education is extremely important. In the process of activity, the child has a certain attitude towards the educational influence coming from outside. This attitude represents the inner needs and desires of the individual.

of psychologists and pedagogues show that the influence of external factors (both positive and negative) on a person depends on the child's attitude towards them. The needs of the child's personal experience determine his attitude to external influences and are reflected in his behavior. Therefore, organizing children's activities is not enough. In order to properly educate, it is necessary to know how to understand, evaluate, feel the attitude of the student towards this activity, how to evaluate and feel what he is aiming for from them. It should also be taken into account that all this happens on the basis of communication with different people, relationships in the team. As the child grows up, these connections and relationships become more complex and affect the child's development either positively or negatively. That's why education envisages regular influence, because in this way, the demands of the society on the individual become an internal need that governs the behavior of the student.

In the process of education, it is necessary to develop not only the student's mind, but also his feelings, and to form moral skills and habits in him that are in accordance with the moral requirements of the society. To achieve this, the student's mind (on the basis of the educational process), emotions (in class and extracurricular activities) and will (in the process of organizing activities, managing behavior) are regularly influenced. If any of these (consciousness, emotions, will) are neglected while educating the student, it will be difficult to achieve the goal. Therefore, the educational process is multifaceted and complex. The process of education in school is a continuous process, it is led by a teacher, an educator, and he determines the necessary goal of education for the given time, the activities that serve to solve this goal. By ensuring the

participation of students in these activities, it creates conditions for social, community and friendship relations and relationships between them.

Through the participation of students in activities, their independence and creative initiative will be achieved. It is in this process that the child's views, beliefs and his own point of view on events are formed and strengthened. These determine how the child reacts to environmental influences.

Thus, school education consists of the process of formation and maturation of the human personality, and its content is not in separate subjects, as in education, but in the life-activities and interactions of students. These are the characteristics of the educational process.

Pedagogical requirement in the process of education

Pedagogical demand is the initial method in the process of education, which ensures the stimulation or stopping of certain activities of the student and the manifestation of specific practical and human qualities.

The method of demand helps to form many moral qualities of students, at the same time, it plays a special role in the development of responsibility and demand in students.

If we look at the single pedagogical requirements, only in our society, the pedagogical requirement can become an effective method of the educational process in strengthening the spiritual and political unity of the people.

While working with students, organizing their activities, the teacher encourages certain actions of students with his instructions. In the process of educational and educational work, he gives them specific comments, reprimands or encourages them, and concludes. Some of his orders are short and blunt, almost coercive, while others take the form of broad explanatory guidelines. Some of them were created due to the need to attract students to work, others were created due to the need to make adjustments to the acquisition of certain skills and competencies of children; some stop students from making unnecessary and inappropriate actions, while others reinforce and support successful actions. It is impossible to imagine the organization of educational and socially useful activities of students without the demand of the pedagogue.

An experienced pedagogue goes to children with a wide program of activities, each of his pupils knows exactly what to do and when. After all, requirements are only a means of implementing this program in their work and behavior. We will look at the main types and forms of pedagogical requirements in the process of education .

Educator's requirements can be indirect requirements, where the educator expects them to achieve certain actions.

The requirements of the teacher are instrumental requirements, in which the teacher with his requirements creates further requirements in children in relation to their friends. The main forms of requirements, the choice of one or another form of this method arise from two main conditions, two factors of the pedagogical situation.

The first factor is the attitude of the one from whom the request is made towards the requester.

The second factor is the pupil's attitude to the activity encouraged by the pedagogue. In general, we describe these relationships as positive, neutral, and negative, although in practice these relationships can take many forms.

Now let's turn to the demand forms. The request may be blunt, with the teacher's appeal having a clear instruction expressed in a firm, bold tone.

Direct demand is especially effective in the first days of working with students. If there is no sincere, transparent, convincing, intense and firm demand, it is impossible to start the educational process, therefore, if anyone thinks to start work from the hesitant ones, he will make a mistake. It should also be noted that the direct request is often used in situations where the student has a neutral attitude towards the pedagogue or the activity he started. In such a situation, it is especially important to observe the following rules of direct, unmediated demand.

The first rule: as a rule, the demand should be positive, that is, it should cause absolutely certain behavior, not simply prohibit or stop children's actions. Of course, the teacher's prohibitions are used especially in cases where students violate the established rules of behavior in various ways. However, the main content of the demands of pedagogues is not prohibitions.

The second rule: the exact requirement should be in the form of a guide, that is, it should be unambiguous, clear and understandable. At the beginning, when encouraging new actions of students, the requirement seems to be combined with guidance, which clearly defines them.

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